

Epoxy/cyclic olefin copolymer/carbon structural composite with electro- activated self-healing properties

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WHY COMPOSITE
MATERIALS ARE SO
IMPORTANT?

Introduction

Introduction

High strength-to-weight ratio

High stiffness-to-weight ratio

High fatigue resistance

PRECEDENCE
RESEARCH

Composites market size [USD Billion]

High thermal stability

Design flexibility

High durability

Introduction

Self healing composite

Self-healing composite aims at the restoration of a lost functionality in a specific application in order to extend the service life of the whole system

Matrix

High mechanical properties
Stable at high temperature

Healing agent

Low melting or softening point
High flowability

Aim of the work

Self-healing carbon fiber epoxy composite

Healing agent deposited through Jet spinning

Healing agent

Interlaminar fracture
toughness tests

Deposition of the healing agent

Cyclic olefinic Copolymer (COC)
TOPAS 9506F-500
COC dissolved in p-xylene (0.15 g/ml)
N₂ flux = 100 ml/min

**COC
content
[wt%]**

6.4 ± 0.2

**COC
content
[wt%]**

10.4 ± 1.0

Composite production

Elan-tech® EC 157.1
resin

Elan-tech® W 342
hardener

100:30

Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding

Curing 8 h RT + 15 h 60 °C

EP-CF

EP-4COC-CF

EP-8COC-CF

Flexural tests

ILSS

G_{IC}

Healing Process

Healing process performed at **110 °C**

through **Joule effect**

Applied Pressure: 0.5 MPa

Time: 20 min

$$\text{Healing Efficiency } (\eta_{GI}) = \frac{G_{I,Healed}}{G_{I,Virgin}} \cdot 100 [\%]$$

$$\text{Healing Efficiency } (\eta_P) = \frac{P_{Healed}}{P_{Virgin}} \cdot 100 [\%]$$

Results and Discussions

Flexural properties
ASTM D790, Instron® 5969, 50 kN

Interlaminar shear strength
ASTM D2344, Instron® 5969, 50 kN, 1 mm/min

Results and Discussions

Interlaminar fracture toughness
ASTM D5528-21, Instron® 5969, 1 kN

Results and Discussions

Interlaminar fracture toughness
ASTM D5528-21, Instron® 5969, 1 kN

Partial recovery of the mechanical properties

Results and Discussions

Scanning Electron
Microscope
Zeiss - SUPRA[®]40
Fractured Surfaces
Voltage = 3.5 kV
Pt:Pd (80:20)

Before
healing

EP-CF

EP-4COC-CF

EP-8COC-CF

After
healing

Conclusion

Deposition of **COC microfibers** on unidirectional carbon fiber fabrics through **jet-spinning**

The deposited **COC microfibers** led to a worsening of the **mechanical properties** of the composites.

Through the addition of **8 wt% of COC microfibers**, an **healing efficiency** up to **33.7 %** was obtained

Future perspective

Production of **intrinsic self-healing** thermosetting composites by directly 3D printing the healing agents on top of the fibers

Design of a **melt electro writing** process for improving of the overall mechanical properties of the **self-healing composites**

Study of the **interfacial adhesion** between the **healing agent** and the **fiber**

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